

Determining the Relationships of Employee Resilience and Organizational Culture with Levels of Employee Work Engagement

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Abstract: The objective is to assess whether the extent to which employee resilience and organizational culture would be significantly related to and statistically predict the three facets of employee work engagement. Resilience was measured by four facets (Determination, Endurance, Adaptability, and Recuperability); and Organization Culture was measured for three types (Bureaucratic, Innovative, and Supportive). The dependent measures were the three facets of Work Engagement (Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical). This research by questionnaire was conducted in 2023. The questionnaires completed by 316 full-time workers revealed that all four facets of employee resilience had significant positive correlations with all three types of work engagement. Also, all three facets of work engagement were significantly higher in Innovative and Supportive cultures compared to Bureaucratic cultures. The regression analyses performed showed that the resilience factors of Determination and Adaptability were strong positive predictors of all three facets of work engagement. Furthermore, Innovative culture had additional positive effects on all three facets of work engagement; while Supportive culture had an additional positive effect on Emotional Work Engagement. The implications of the results for management are also discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Personal resilience, organizational culture, work engagement.

Determinar as relações entre a resiliência dos colaboradores e a cultura organizacional com os níveis de envolvimento dos colaboradores no trabalho

Resumo: O objetivo é avaliar até que ponto a resiliência dos colaboradores e a cultura organizacional estariam significativamente relacionadas e se preveriam estatisticamente as três facetas do envolvimento dos colaboradores no trabalho. A resiliência foi medida por quatro facetas (Determinação, Resistência, Adaptabilidade, e Recuperabilidade); e a Cultura Organizacional foi medida para três tipos (Burocrática, Inovadora, e de Apoio). As medidas dependentes foram as três facetas do Envolvimento no Trabalho (Cognitiva, Emocional, e Física). Esta pesquisa por questionário foi realizada em 2023. Os questionários preenchidos por 316 trabalhadores a tempo inteiro revelaram que todas as quatro facetas da resiliência dos colaboradores tinham correlações positivas significativas com todos os três tipos de envolvimento no trabalho. Além disso, todas as três facetas do envolvimento no trabalho foram significativamente maiores nas culturas inovadoras e de apoio em comparação com as culturas burocráticas. As análises de regressão realizadas evidenciaram que os fatores de resiliência Determinação e Adaptabilidade eram fortes preditores positivos de todas as três facetas do envolvimento no trabalho. Além disso, a cultura inovadora teve efeitos positivos adicionais em todas as três facetas do envolvimento no trabalho; enquanto a cultura de apoio teve um efeito positivo adicional no envolvimento emocional no trabalho. As implicações dos resultados para a gestão também são discutidas no artigo.

Palavras-chave: Resiliência pessoal, cultura organizacional, engajamento no trabalho.

1. Introduction

In analyzing Gallop poll results on work engagement, Buckingham (1999) found that fewer than 20 percent of (less than one out of five) employees could be described as work engaged. That is considered problematic because managers in all types of organizations prefer employees who are interested in their work and enjoy doing their work, namely, employees who are work engaged. That is evident in many studies, which have shown that organizations benefit from having work-engaged employees. For example, they benefit because they have employees with “improved work productivity, better employee retention, and reduced overall health care costs” (Attridge, 2009, p.389).

Furthermore, high levels of employee work engagement also benefit employees. For example, work engagement was found to have a significant positive relationship with life satisfaction (Hakanen & Schaufeli, 2012). Also, employees who enjoy their work have increased feelings of their own career success, indicating good person-organization fit, which, in turn, is a positive predictor of work engagement (Kuok & Taormina, 2017, 2022).

At the same time, however, organizations have different cultures, and employees have different personal characteristics. Those factors suggest that there could be several types of mismatches between the employees’ personalities and the organizations in which they work; which might account for the low incidence of work-engaged employees. Also, a recent study on work engagement among healthcare workers indicated that workers and managers need to recognize the importance of increased work engagement (Borges et al., 2024).

Hence, more research is needed to examine what factors encourage employees with different personality characteristics to be work engaged in different types of organizational cultures. Therefore, this research focused on the personal resilience facets of Determination, Endurance, Adaptability, and Recuperability, along with three types of Organizational Culture, namely, Bureaucratic, Innovative, and Supportive, to investigate how employee personal resilience and organizational cultures relate to three facets of employee work engagement, namely, Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement.

To investigate the relationships between the variables, an empirical study was conducted, using a structured questionnaire to obtain data from working adults. Was validated questionnaires from 316 full-time workers that were working in a Macau business district.

2. Literature Review

Work engagement has become a popular topic of study in the field of management in recent decades, but there have been various types, conceptualizations, and measures of work engagement variables. Essentially, there are two main approaches to the study of work engagement. The original approach was proposed by Kahn (1990), a pioneer in the study of work engagement, who viewed it as a variable with three components, namely, cognitive, emotional, and physical engagement, each with its own continuum that could have different levels, ranging from very low to very high. Other authors regarded work engagement as a one-dimensional concept, measuring it as if it were the opposite of burnout (Maslach & Leiter, 1997); and in a variation of that same approach, it was viewed multidimensionally, which viewed work engagement is the “antipode” of burnout (Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá, & Bakker, 2002). Unfortunately, the latter approach was mainly grounded in burnout, i.e., as its negative, while disregarding the original, positivist

concept of work engagement, and thereby lost the significance of Kahn's three dimensions. Kuok and Taormina (2017), however, based their work in Kahn's concept, from which they developed definitions, and created valid and reliable measures for each of Kahn's cognitive, emotional, and physical work engagement facets.

2.1. Cognitive Work Engagement Defined

Cognitive Work Engagement is defined as "the intentional and actively focused awareness of one's tasks, objectives, or organizational activities that is characterized by willingly calling one's attention to and having positive thoughts about one's work, with the purpose of improving one's effectiveness at those tasks, objectives, or activities" (Kuok & Taormina, 2017, p.266).

2.2. Emotional Work Engagement Defined

Emotional Work Engagement is defined as "the willing attachment to tasks, objectives, or organizational activities that is characterized by having positive feelings, such as pride, enthusiasm, and excitement, about actively executing and completing those tasks, objectives, or activities" (Kuok & Taormina, 2017, p.266).

2.3. Physical Work Engagement Defined

Physical Work Engagement is defined as "the bodily involvement in tasks, objectives, or organizational activities by intentionally and voluntarily utilizing one's energy and effort to execute and complete those tasks, objectives, or activities" (Kuok & Taormina, 2017, p.267).

2.4. Resilience in relation to Work Engagement

This study used a definition of Resilience from a literature review of adult resilience: "Adult personal resilience is a multifaceted construct that includes a person's determination and ability to endure, adapt, and recover from adversity" (Taormina, 2015, p.36). For example, Masten and Reed (2002) mentioned that resilience is characterized by patterns of positive adaptation in response to significant adversity or risk. Using that idea, research has found that resilience is a powerful positive predictor of occupational health (Kuok, Chio, & Pun, 2022), suggesting that resilience is a reliable variable for studying organizational behavior. Furthermore, Luthans (2002) advocated that research in organizational behavior should take a positivist approach, e.g., emotionally strong employees are better able to contribute to organizational goals. Also, employees with higher self-efficacy, have more perseverance (connoting work engagement) and higher resistance to stress (connoting resilience), which, in turn, generate higher performance (Mager, 1992).

Specifically, regarding resilience and work engagement, Malik and Garg (2017) argued that there is minimal literature that examined the relationship between those two constructs, and found that resilient individuals had higher levels of work engagement (Malik & Garg, 2017). Other research indicated that resilience and work engagement are positively correlated, suggesting that (among Asians) individuals who exhibit resilient behaviors may experience higher levels of work engagement (Amir & Mangundjaya, 2021; Lyu et al., 2020). There is also evidence that being resilient at work can be a precursor of work engagement, and that employees who engage in group work can better navigate adverse experiences (Xie, 2021).

However, there are some weaknesses with most previous studies. For example, the Malik and Garg (2017) study used a measure of resilience with inherent weaknesses. That is, the items measured a variety of factors that could not be considered as either resilience (e.g., helping work colleagues) or work engagement (e.g., conscientiously eating well); or combined resilience and work engagement in the same statements, which could yield high correlations between the two measures. Another common problem is that many studies used a negative measure of work engagement, namely, a measure that was based on the negative concept of burnout, rather than Kahn's (1970) positive-based three facets of work engagement.

Hence, whereas previous research indicated that there should be a positive relationship between employee personal resilience and work engagement, it is necessary to test that relationship empirically, using positive measures of resilience and work engagement, to ascertain the validity of that relationship. Consequently, the present study used Taormina's (2015) four domains of adult personal resilience, namely, Determination, Endurance, Adaptability, and Recuperability, to empirically validate their respective relationships with the three Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical facets of work engagement. The hypotheses regarding all the facets of both constructs are shown in the next section of this article.

3. Research Hypotheses

Seven hypotheses were made to assess the significance of the expected relationships between: (a) each of the four Resilience facets and the three Work Engagement types (yielding four hypotheses); and (b) the three types of Organizational Culture on the three types of Work Engagement (which yielded three hypotheses). Each hypothesis is explained below, followed by its exact wording.

3.1. Resilience in relation to Work Engagement

Based on the definition of each facet of Resilience, i.e., Determination, Endurance, Adaptability, and Recuperability, four hypotheses were made to evaluate their respective relationships with the three facets of work engagement, namely, Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement. Accordingly, based on the definitions, the first four hypotheses were as follows:

Determination resilience is defined as "the willpower and firmness of purpose that a person has and the decision to persevere and/or to succeed" (Taormina, 2015, p.36). Whereas determination is related to being goal-oriented, a worker with a high level of determination should be more likely to set goals for high levels of achievement at work. And therefore, according to Kahn's (1970) theory, that worker should be more cognitively, emotionally, and physically work engaged. Thus:

H1: Determination will have significant positive correlations with (a) Cognitive, (b) Emotional, and (c) Physical work engagement.

Endurance resilience is defined as "the personal strength and fortitude that one possesses to withstand unpleasant or difficult situations without giving up" (Taormina, 2015, p.37). Endurance refers to the ability of a person to physically as well as cognitively (and perhaps emotionally) live through certain kinds of stress in life, including at work. Thus, a worker with a high level of endurance should be more able to cope with obstacles at work, and therefore be more cognitively, emotionally, and physically work engaged. Thus:

H2: Endurance will have significant positive correlations with (a) Cognitive, (b) Emotional, and (c) Physical work engagement.

Adaptability resilience is defined as “the capacity to be flexible and resourceful and to cope with adverse environments and adjust oneself to fit into changing conditions” (Taormina, 2015, p.37). Adaptability refers to making a conscious effort to change one’s thinking and/or behavior. Therefore, a worker, who has a high level of adaptability is more willing to find ways to adjust to challenges, and thereby is more likely to cope with obstacles at work, and therefore be more cognitively, emotionally, and physically work engaged. Thus:

H3: Adaptability will have significant positive correlations with (a) Cognitive, (b) Emotional, and (c) Physical work engagement.

Recuperability resilience is defined as “the ability to recover, physically and cognitively, from various types of harm, setbacks, or difficulties in order to return to and reestablish one’s usual condition” (Taormina, 2015, p.37). Recuperability is a characteristic of resilience that enables individuals to recover. Thus, a worker who has a high level of recuperability is more successful in finding ways to improve a stressful situation, and thereby be more likely to bounce back, and therefore be more cognitively, emotionally, and physically work engaged. Thus:

H4: Recuperability will have significant positive correlations with (a) Cognitive, (b) Emotional, and (c) Physical work engagement.

3.2. Organizational Culture in relation to Work Engagement

Culture was defined by Triandis (1996) operationally, in a clear, concise, and relevant way as “the values, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that are shared by a group of people” (Triandis, 1996, p.407); which is characteristic of groups, organizations, and societies. Hence, it applies to Organizational Culture, because it refers to the ways people behave in groups in organizations. Types of organizations can be characterized in certain ways.

Indeed, Wallach (1993) described three types of organizational culture: Bureaucratic, which is hierarchical, orderly, programmed, and highly regulated; Innovative, which values creativity, enterprise, being adventurous, and results-oriented; and Supportive, which advocates fairness, positive social interaction, trust, and collaborative behavior. Supportive and Innovative cultures are often viewed as having positive effects on organizational behaviors (Nisa & Fayaz, 2018). Bureaucratic culture, however, is typically thought to have a negative effect on organizational behavior. The three types of organizational culture were examined using these facets of work engagement, as shown in the next three hypotheses.

Supportive Culture refers to organizations in which employees are given positive reinforcement, while also being held responsible for their actions. This type of culture encourages employees to take responsibility for their work, building relationships, and being creative and productive. Research has found that supportive culture has a positive impact on work engagement (Rofcanin, Las Heras, & Bakker, 2017). Also, Aktar and Pangil (2018) found that supportive culture moderated the relationship between human resource management (HRM) and work engagement. Although they also found a significant positive correlation between supportive organizational culture and work engagement, their measure (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004) did not assess Kahn’s three facets of work engagement.

The present authors consider that knowing how supportive culture relates to each facet of work engagement would be more informative. Hence, measures of Kahn's three facets of work engagement were used in this study. Thus, in supportive organizations, in which work is flexible and collaborative, employees should have high levels of engagement as it makes them feel accepted, feel that their contributions are important, and that they belong. Thus:

H5: Supportive Culture will have significant positive correlations with (a) Cognitive, (b) Emotional, and (c) Physical work engagement.

Innovative Culture encourages employees to "think outside the box" and come up with new ideas and solutions. This type of culture encourages experimentation and risk-taking, while rewarding creativity and new thinking. Studies have found that innovative culture leads to higher job satisfaction (Berson, Oreg, & Dvir, 2008; Odom, Boxx, & Dunn, 1990) and organizational commitment (Alvi et al., 2014). Thus, employees feel supported and valued by the organization and, in return, are motivated to commit to the organization's goals. Thus:

H6: Innovative Culture will have significant positive correlations with (a) Cognitive, (b) Emotional, and (c) Physical work engagement.

Bureaucratic Culture is characterized by stringent rules, regulations, and guidelines that tend to limit creativity and risk-taking. Research has found that workers in bureaucratic cultures have lower job satisfaction, less job involvement, and experience higher levels of stress (Wallach, 1983; Taormina, 2015). Thus, organizational cultures that are highly bureaucratic can lead to lower work engagement among employees because they do not support independent decision-making, and employees may feel a lack of autonomy while being disconnected from the company's vision and values. Therefore:

H7: Bureaucratic Culture will have significant negative correlations with (a) Cognitive, (b) Emotional, and (c) Physical work engagement.

4. Methodology

To investigate the relationships between the variables, an empirical, data-gathering method used a structured questionnaire to obtain data from working adults. That method was appropriate as the study focused on individual employee personality characteristics, namely: personal resilience; their personal assessments of how work-engaged they believed they were; and their assessments of the cultural characteristics of the organizations in which they worked.

4.1. Respondents

The respondents were 316 (148 males and 168 females) full-time workers from a business district in a local city where the researchers' university was located. All respondents were ethnic Chinese, whose ages ranged from 18 to 64 years, with an average age of 31.55 years (SD = 10.02). Regarding educational achievement, 10 completed primary school (or less), 122 secondary school, 166 a bachelor degree, and 18 completed a master degree (or above).

4.2. Measures

A structured questionnaire obtained the data for all the variables. All the measures were from existing questionnaires that were originally created in English and had good to excellent validities and reliabilities. Whereas English was not the respondents' native

language, translation and back-translation of the questionnaire were conducted by bilingual expert linguists. Respondents were asked the extent to which they agreed or disagreed that the statements (items) described them and the organization in which they worked. All of the items used a 5-point Likert-type response scale, which ranged from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

4.2.1. Work Engagement

This variable was measured by the Work Engagement Inventory (Kuok & Taormina, 2017), which has three facets, namely, Cognitive (original alpha = .88), Emotional (original alpha = .78), and Physical Work Engagement (original alpha = .88). Sample items were: For Cognitive, "My thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work"; for Emotional, "I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working"; and for Physical, "I am frequently energized by my work." The Cronbach alpha reliabilities for those facets of work engagement in this study were .80, .91, and .92, respectively.

4.2.2. Resilience

This variable was measured by the Adult Personal Resilience Scale (Taormina, 2015), which has four components, namely, Determination (original alpha = .83), Endurance (original alpha = .76), Adaptability (original alpha = .78), and Recuperability (original alpha = .77). Sample items were: For Determination, "Once I set a goal, I am determined to achieve it"; for Endurance, "I am able to live through difficult times"; for Adaptability, "I have the ability to adapt to difficult situations"; and for Recuperability, "I recover from any misfortune that happens to me." The Cronbach alpha reliabilities for those facets of the personal resilience variable in this study were .86, .85, .85 and .93, respectively.

4.2.3. Organizational Culture

This variable was measured by Wallach's (1983) Organizational Culture Scale, which has three facets, namely: Bureaucratic (original alpha = .82), Innovative (original alpha = .88), and Supportive Culture (original alpha = .79). Sample items were: For Bureaucratic, "Hierarchical"; for Innovative, "Creative"; and for Supportive, "Encouraging." Respondents were asked how well the adjectives describe their organizations on a response scale that ranged from 1 (not at all) to 5 (almost always). The Cronbach alpha reliabilities for those types of organizational culture in this study were .76, .73, and .85, respectively.

4.3. Procedure

The study was conducted in 2023 over a period of approximately three months. As it studied full-time workers, the data came from business districts in Macau. To preclude ethics concerns in the workplace, people were not approached when they were working, i.e., to avoid any sense of being monitored by their employers. Thus, potential respondents were approached in public places near where many businesses are located during lunch breaks, after work, or on weekends. Choosing public locations also ensured that the respondents would have sufficient spare time to complete the questionnaire.

In accord with international guidelines for the ethical treatment of research participants, the guidelines of the American Psychological Association were followed. Ethics approval was obtained prior to conducting the study by submitting its description

and methodology to a research ethics committee chair of a local university, who approved it.

A systematic sampling method was used, i.e., for every fifth adult passing by, potential respondents were approached individually. Informed consent was used, both verbally and in writing on the questionnaire. Thus, every respondent was informed of the purpose of the study, asked if they were full-time workers, and if so, were asked to fill in the questionnaire. Those who agreed were handed the questionnaire. Of the 448 people asked, 316 completed the questionnaires, yielding a response rate of 70.53%.

5. Results

All statistical analyses in this study used the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The results begin with statistical tests of the reliability and validity of the data, i.e., tests for multicollinearity and common method bias. Next, comparisons of the variable means were computed to examine the levels of employee Resilience and Work Engagement within each of the three Organization Cultures. Then, correlations were computed to test the hypotheses. Finally, regression analyses were run to ascertain the relative predictabilities of the resilience and culture factors on employee work engagement.

5.1. Test for Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity is a statistical phenomenon in which predictor variables in a multiple regression model are highly correlated, which could lead to inaccuracy in the statistical analyses. This was assessed by a “tolerance” ($1 - R^2$) test for each independent variable. According to Hair, Anderson, Tatham, and Black (1998, pp. 191-193), a tolerance value of less than .10 is problematic. This study used all the independent variables (for the planned regressions), and regressed each one on all the other independent variables (excluding the demographics as many are naturally correlated, e.g., age and education). The tolerance values for the independent variables ranged from .47 to .81, which were all above the .10 cutoff, indicating that multicollinearity was not a concern in this study.

5.2. Test for Common Method Bias

Common Method Bias is a statistical phenomenon in which statistical relationships may be based on the measurement method as opposed to measurement of the constructs. This was assessed by factor analyzing all the variables in this study together, and using the “maximum-likelihood” approach with a forced, one-factor solution (see Harman, 1960). If a ratio of the resultant Chi-square value divided by the degrees of freedom is less than 2.00:1, that would suggest common-method bias (i.e., a single factor). For this study, the ratio was 15.60:1, indicating that common-method bias was not a concern.

5.3. Means Comparisons

Although no hypotheses were made about differences within the organizational cultures, there were significant differences between the employees’ levels of Resilience and Work Engagement in certain cultures. Several t-tests were run, by using the means of the three organizational cultures as cutoff points to compare the workers in high and low Bureaucratic, Innovative, Supportive cultures.

Determination resilience was significantly higher among workers in high Bureaucratic cultures ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.59$) compared to workers in low Bureaucratic cultures ($M = 3.63$, $SD = 0.66$) ($t(314) = 3.192$; $p < .005$). Similarly, Determination was significantly higher

among workers in high Innovative cultures ($M= 3.86$, $SD=0.55$) compared to workers in low Innovative cultures ($M= 3.62$, $SD=0.70$) ($t(314) = 3.514$; $p < .005$).

Adaptability resilience was found to be significantly higher among workers in high Bureaucratic cultures ($M= 3.81$, $SD=0.58$) compared to workers in low Bureaucratic cultures ($M= 3.69$, $SD=0.51$) ($t(314) = 2.319$; $p < .05$). Likewise, Adaptability resilience was significantly higher among workers in high Innovative cultures ($M= 3.82$, $SD=0.51$) versus workers in low Innovative cultures ($M= 3.68$, $SD=0.59$) ($t(314) = 2.045$; $p < .05$).

Regarding Endurance resilience and Recuperability resilience, no significant differences among employees were found in any of the three cultures. Furthermore, no differences in any facet of resilience were found in high versus low Supportive cultures. That is, employee resilience was approximately equal in the Supportive organizational cultures.

For Work Engagement, all three facets were found to be significantly higher in Innovative and Supportive cultures. Specifically, Cognitive work engagement was found to be significantly higher among workers in high Innovative cultures ($M= 3.54$, $SD=0.64$) than in low Innovative cultures ($M= 3.26$, $SD=0.71$) ($t(314) = 3.787$; $p < .001$), while employee Cognitive work engagement was also significantly higher in high Supportive cultures ($M= 3.52$, $SD=0.63$) than in low Supportive cultures ($M= 3.30$, $SD=0.73$) ($t(314) = 2.891$; $p < .005$).

Emotional work engagement was found to be significantly higher among workers in high Innovative cultures ($M= 3.79$, $SD=0.65$) than in low Innovative cultures ($M= 3.33$, $SD=0.82$) ($t(314) = 5.484$; $p < .001$). Similarly, Emotional work engagement was significantly higher in high Supportive cultures ($M= 3.79$, $SD=0.62$) than in low Supportive cultures ($M= 3.33$, $SD=0.84$) ($t(314) = 5.492$; $p < .001$).

Additionally, Physical work engagement was found to be higher among workers in high Innovative cultures ($M= 3.53$, $SD=0.72$) than in low Innovative cultures ($M= 3.00$, $SD=0.84$) ($t(314) = 6.058$, $p < .001$). Likewise, Physical work engagement was found to be higher among workers in high Supportive cultures ($M= 3.52$, $SD=0.71$) compared to low Supportive cultures ($M= 3.01$, $SD=0.85$) ($t(314) = 5.848$; $p < .001$).

There were no significant differences found in any of the three facets of employee work engagement in high versus low levels of Bureaucratic organizational cultures.

5.4. Correlation Analyses

Pearson correlation tests (r) were conducted to compute the inter-correlations that the dependent variables, namely, the three facets of work engagement, had with the antecedent variables, namely, the four facets of resilience, and the three organizational cultures. Also, support or non-support of the hypotheses are specified in each paragraph below.

For resilience, all four aspects had significant, positive correlations with all three facets of work engagement. Determination resilience had highly significant, positive correlations with Cognitive work engagement ($r = .35$; $p < .001$), Emotional work engagement ($r = .36$; $p < .001$), and Physical work engagement ($r = .37$; $p < .001$), which supported H(1a) to H(1c). Endurance resilience also had highly significant positive correlations with Cognitive work engagement ($r = .32$; $p < .001$), Emotional work engagement ($r = .34$; $p < .001$), and Physical work engagement ($r = .35$; $p < .001$), which supported H(2a) to H(2c). Adaptability resilience likewise had highly significant positive correlations with Cognitive work engagement ($r = .44$; $p < .001$), with Emotional work

engagement ($r = .40$; $p < .001$), and with Physical work engagement ($r = .41$; $p < .001$), which supported H(3a) to H(3c). Recuperability resilience also had highly significant positive correlations with Cognitive work engagement ($r = .33$; $p < .001$), Emotional work engagement ($r = .31$; $p < .001$), and Physical work engagement ($r = .34$; $p < .001$), which supported H(4a) to H(4c).

For Organizational Culture, Bureaucratic culture was expected to have significant negative correlations with all three facets of work engagement. But, instead, had significant positive correlations with Emotional work engagement ($r = .18$, $p < .005$), and Physical work engagement ($r = .14$; $p < .05$), which was opposite of the hypothesis, and a non-significant correlation with Cognitive work engagement; therefore, H(5a) to H(5c) were not supported.

Innovative organizational culture had highly significant positive correlations with Cognitive work engagement ($r = .29$; $p < .001$), Emotional work engagement ($r = .37$; $p < .001$), and Physical work engagement ($r = .37$; $p < .001$), which supported H(6a) to H(6c).

Supportive organizational culture had highly significant positive correlations with Cognitive work engagement ($r = .19$; $p < .005$), Emotional work engagement ($r = .38$; $p < .001$), and Physical work engagement ($r = .29$; $p < .001$), which supported H(7a) to H(7c). All these correlations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Means, standard deviations, and intercorrelations among the variables (N=316)

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Cognitive Work Engagement	3.42	.69	(.80)									
2. Emotional Work Engagement	3.58	.77	.68****	(.91)								
3. Physical Work Engagement	3.29	.82	.65****	.76****	(.92)							
4. Resilience - Determination	3.76	.63	.35****	.36****	.37****	(.86)						
5. Resilience - Endurance	3.75	.61	.32****	.34****	.35****	.48****	(.85)					
6. Resilience - Adaptability	3.75	.55	.44****	.40****	.41****	.50****	.60****	(.85)				
7. Resilience - Recuperability	3.65	.67	.33****	.31****	.34****	.40****	.67****	.61****	(.93)			
8. Bureaucratic culture	3.57	.55	.11	.18***	.14*	.22****	.03	.13*	.04	(.76)		
9. Innovative culture	3.06	.55	.29****	.37****	.37****	.25****	.15**	.14*	.13*	.20****	(.73)	
10. Supportive culture	3.54	.63	.19***	.38****	.29****	.15**	.12*	.15**	.10	.39****	.61****	(.85)

Note: Reliabilities are in parentheses on the diagonal. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .005$; **** $p < .001$.

5.5. Regression Analyses

Hierarchical, stepwise, linear regression analyses were performed using the three facets of Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement as the dependent (criterion) variables. Stepwise regressions were run identify the most significant predictors from among the antecedent variables on work engagement. The four facets of resilience (Determination, Endurance, Adaptability, and Recuperability) were used as the potential predictors in Step 1; and the three types of organizational culture (Bureaucratic, Innovative, and Supportive) were used in Step 2, to test whether they would have additional effects on work engagement.

In the regression for Cognitive work engagement, in Step 1, the two resilience variables of Adaptability and Determination entered the equation as predictors. The strongest predictor was Adaptability, with $\beta = .352$, $\Delta R^2 = .19$, $p < .001$; and Determination also entered the equation as a significant predictor, with $\beta = .117$, $\Delta R^2 = .03$, $p < .05$. Then, in Step 2, among the organizational culture variables, Innovative culture became an additional significant predictor, with $\beta = .210$, $\Delta R^2 = .04$, $p < .001$. Together, these variables explained 26% of the variance for predicting Cognitive work engagement, $R^2 = .26$, $F(3,312) = 35.86$, $p < .001$. These results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Hierarchical stepwise regressions for Cognitive work engagement, using the resilience and organizational cultures as predictors (N =315).

Variables	Beta	t-value	ΔR^2	R^2	F(3,312)
Cognitive Work Engagement				.26	35.86****
<u>Block 1</u>					
Resilience - Determination	.117	2.04*	.03		
Resilience - Endurance	.027	0.43			
Resilience - Adaptability	.352	6.25****	.19		
Resilience - Recoverability	.064	1.04			
<u>Block 2</u>					
Bureaucratic culture	-.003	-0.07			
Innovative culture	.210	4.17****	.04		
Supportive culture	-.018	-0.29			

Note: * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .005$; **** $p < .001$.

In the regression for Emotional work engagement, in Step 1, the two resilience variables of Adaptability and Determination entered the equation as predictors. Similarly, the strongest predictor was Adaptability, with $\beta = .267$, $\Delta R^2 = .16$, $p < .001$; and Determination also entered the equation as a significant predictor, with $\beta = .157$, $\Delta R^2 = .04$, $p < .01$. In Step 2, the organizational culture variables of Supportive and Innovative culture entered the equation as additional predictors. Supportive culture had $\beta = .215$, $\Delta R^2 = .09$, $p < .001$. And Innovative culture had $\beta = .166$, $\Delta R^2 = .02$, $p < .01$. Together, these four variables explained 31% of the variance for predicting Emotional work engagement, $R^2 = .31$, $F(4,311) = 34.45$, $p < .001$. These results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Hierarchical stepwise regressions for Emotional work engagement, using the resilience and organizational cultures as predictors (N =315).

Variables	Beta	t-value	ΔR^2	R^2	F(4,311)
Emotional Work Engagement				.31	34.45****
<u>Block 1</u>					
Resilience - Determination	.157	2.81**	.04		
Resilience - Endurance	.096	1.57			
Resilience - Adaptability	.267	4.87****	.16		
Resilience - Recoverability	.072	1.20			
<u>Block 2</u>					
Bureaucratic culture	-.004	-0.07			
Innovative culture	.166	2.74**	.02		
Supportive culture	.215	3.60****	.09		

Note: * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .005$; **** $p < .001$.

In the regression for Physical work engagement, in Step 1, similarly, the two resilience variables of Adaptability and Determination entered the equation as predictors. Once again, the strongest predictor was Adaptability, with $\beta = .285$, $\Delta R^2 = .17$, $p < .001$. Likewise, Determination also entered the equation as a significant predictor, with $\beta = .160$, $\Delta R^2 = .03$, $p < .05$. In Step 2, the organizational culture variable of Innovative culture also entered the equation as an additional predictor, with $\beta = .285$, $\Delta R^2 = .08$, $p < .001$. Together, these three variables explained 28% of the variance for predicting Physical work engagement, $R^2 = .28$, $F(3,312) = 40.29$, $p < .001$. These results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Hierarchical stepwise regressions for Physical work engagement, using the resilience and organizational cultures as predictors (N =315).

Variables	Beta	t-value	ΔR^2	R^2	F(3,312)
Physical Work Engagement				.28	40.29****
<u>Block 1</u>					
Resilience - Determination	.160	2.82*	.03		
Resilience - Endurance	.102	1.64			
Resilience - Adaptability	.285	5.14****	.17		
Resilience - Recoverability	.103	1.69			
<u>Block 2</u>					
Bureaucratic culture	.008	0.16			
Innovative culture	.285	5.75****	.08		
Supportive culture	.082	1.36			

Note: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.005$; **** $p < 0.001$.

6. Discussion

6.1. Employee resilience and work engagement in different organizational cultures

The results of the current study provided a clearer picture of how employee resilience and work engagement can vary when working in organizations with different cultures, i.e., in Bureaucratic, Innovative, and Supportive organizational cultures. Among the noteworthy findings was that, when organizational cultures were split into high versus low levels in each culture, employee resilience differed depending on the type of organizational culture. That is, employee Determination was significantly higher among workers in high, as opposed to low, levels of Bureaucratic culture, and was also significantly higher among workers in high compared to low levels of Innovative culture. The same result was found for employee Adaptability in high versus low Bureaucratic and Innovative cultures.

These findings strongly suggest ways for employees to endure in Bureaucratic and Innovative organizational cultures. That is, both cultures tend to have management that is very demanding, with strict requirements for their employees. Therefore, to survive in organizations with Bureaucratic and Innovative cultures, employees need to have strong personal resilience, especially the ability to adapt to the demanding characteristics of such organizations, and to remain determined to accomplish their missions.

Similarly, when the organizations' cultures were split into high and low levels, employee work engagement also varied depending on the cultures. For the employees, all three types of work engagement, namely, their Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement, were significantly higher in organizations that had stronger (rather than weaker) Innovative as well as Supportive organizational cultures.

These findings indicate that employees tend to respond very well to organizational cultures (management) that offer them the freedom to use their own ideas, and stimulate their creativity in Innovative Cultures; and are considerate of their individual differences, let them know they are appreciated, and give them encouragement in Supportive cultures.

6.2. Hypotheses support and non-support interpreted

This study confirmed the positive relationship between employee personal resilience and work engagement. First, Hypotheses H1(a-c) through H4(a-c) were all fully supported. They were on employee resilience and work engagement, and all the correlation values for the employees' four types of personal resilience and their three types of work engagement were positive and highly significant, ranging from $r=.31$ to $r=.44$ (all $p < .001$). This is meaningful because the sample of 316 employees were of both genders from many different organizations, and did many different kinds of work. That reflects a connection between people's resilience and their willingness to be engaged with their work. As explained in the formulation of those hypotheses, having a high level of personal resilience can help people in general, and employees in particular, to have positive feelings about the work they do and their success in life.

Hypotheses H5(a-c) and H6(a-c), on organizational culture and work engagement, were also fully supported, shedding greater light on which types of organizational culture could facilitate (or impede) an employee's willingness to become more (or less) work engaged. Innovative and Supportive cultures both had highly significant positive correlations with all three facets of work engagement. For Supportive culture, its correlation with Cognitive work engagement was $r=.19$ ($p < .005$), which supported H(5a); with Emotional work engagement was $r=.38$ ($p < .001$), which supported H(5b); and with Physical work engagement was $r=.29$ ($p < .001$), which supported H(5c). These results support findings by Caesens, Stinglhamber, and Luypaert (2014), whose study found significant positive correlations between perceived organizational support and work engagement, $r=.26$ ($p < .001$), despite their use of an older version of work engagement.

For Innovative culture, the correlations with all three facets of work engagement ranged from $r=.29$ to $r=.37$ (all $p < .001$), which supported H(6a-c). These results support a study by Li et al. (2019) that measured innovative culture in relation to work engagement. Although not measuring organizational culture, per se, they viewed transformational leadership as "innovative." Thus, they measured transformational leadership with (an alternate version of) work engagement, and found that innovative culture (transformational leadership) had a significant positive correlation with work engagement, $r=.36$ ($p < .01$).

Hypothesis 7(a-c), however, regarding Bureaucratic culture and work engagement, did not support the hypothesis for either type of work engagement. It was expected that the restrictive regulations in bureaucratic organizations would relate negatively to all three types of work engagement. Instead, Bureaucratic organizational culture had a non-significant relationship with Cognitive work engagement, H7(a); and had positive relationships with Emotional work engagement, H7(b); and Physical work engagement, H7(c).

The non-significant relationship between Bureaucratic culture and Cognitive work engagement might be explained by the tendency of managers in bureaucratic organizations to give employees mundane tasks which have specified guidelines in how they should be carried out; such that the employees know they do not need to be cognitively involved. In other words, they accept those rules because they know they can

succeed at their tasks without being cognitively engaged, and thus merely follow their manager's instructions.

The unexpected positive correlation that Bureaucratic culture had with Emotional work engagement might be explained by the societal culture. That is, the data were from a Chinese society, which has deeply prescribed values, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that are followed virtually by everyone so that people may live in social harmony. Hence, in Asian society, where the group's harmony and success supersede individual desires, employees would want to get along well with their coworkers to achieve the group's (organization's) objectives. Therefore, Chinese employees might follow an organization's strict rules and prescribed behaviors to ensure the company's success, which, in turn, financially supports the employees.

Hence, people in Asian society willingly follow the strict rules of a bureaucratic company because their society's culture places a high value on social harmony, which they see as coincident with their personal goals (earning a good living). This is an interesting contrast with western societies. That is, as western societies value individual achievement (versus being group-centered), there would be conflict between an "individualistic" employee's personal work values and a bureaucratic organization's culture that requires its employees to work according to strict rules.

Thus, in western societies, a hypothesis which states that individualist employees do not emotionally engage with their work in restrictive organization cultures would be more likely to be supported. In fact, in the Netherlands, Borst, Kruijven, and Lako's (2019) study examined bureaucracy in government organizations with a variable they called "red tape" (regulations and rules that delay decision-making and taking action) and compared it with employees' work engagement. And they found that "red tape" had a significant negative correlation with work engagement, $r = -.17$ ($p < .001$).

However, in Asian societies, which prescribe acquiescing to group goals to maintain social harmony in order to achieve the organization's goals, the benefits of which are shared by the workers, people align their emotions with those of their colleagues (the organization) and thus would be more emotionally work engaged (than people in individualistic societies) in bureaucratic cultures. That is, future research might affirm such a cross-cultural difference by gathering data from both Asian and Western societies on Emotional work engagement and comparing the results.

Also, the slight positive correlation Bureaucratic culture had with Physical engagement might be explained by a willingness of Asian employees to wake up early to be at work on time. That would be a positive willingness because of their preference to keep their jobs (compared to the stronger willingness of work-engaged people who really enjoy their work). That is, having a job with a salary that provides enough money to pay one's living expenses could create a desire to live by the rules of a strict bureaucratic organization, and therefore make a person willing to perform physical tasks efficiently in order to keep one's job, and even (possibly) be rewarded for one's efficiency. In other words, Asian employees might be willing just to complete manual (physical) tasks on time in accord with company rules, and thereby make a good impression on management.

6.3. Regressions impact of employee resilience on their work engagement

Hierarchical, stepwise, linear regression analyses were run to ascertain whether the correlations which the facets of the independent variables had with the criterion variables were strong enough to predict the variance in the three facets of work engagement. Also,

stepwise regressions were run because there were significant intercorrelations among the facets of the independent measures, i.e., to preclude possible multicollinearity. Thus, the regressions using personal resilience are discussed first.

Of the four facets of employee resilience (Determination, Endurance, Adaptability, and Recuperability), Adaptability and Determination were significant predictors of all three types, namely, Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement. While all four facets of adult personal resilience contribute to a person's ability to "bounce back" from difficulties that one faces in life (Taormina, 2015), in the present study, the results of the regressions on what makes employees more work engaged indicated that the two strongest facets of employee personal resilience were Adaptability and Determination.

These results revealed how employees can be more work engaged when companies in which they work experience difficulties. That is, (1) the employees need the will-power to persevere and/or to succeed, e.g., they need to think that any difficulties their company encounters (as happens in every organization) can be overcome by expending personal effort; and (2) the employee must also be willing to adapt in various ways when they or their companies face unfavorable circumstances.

6.4. Regressions for organizational culture on employee work engagement

In addition to assessing the effects of employee resilience on work engagement, the effects of organizational cultures on work engagement were also investigated in (Step 2 of) the regression analyses. Of the three types of culture, Innovative culture had an additional positive impact on all three facets of work engagement. Organizational cultures that place an emphasis on innovativeness need their employees to contribute ideas for those companies to be successful. Therefore, when innovative managers provide opportunities for their employees to think creatively and are open to the employees' suggestions, and also reward workable suggestions, those characteristics could be expected to stimulate the employees. That is, to offer their own ideas (be cognitively work engaged); enjoy working in a place that accepts their individual inputs (be emotionally work engaged); and be willing to perform the work (be physically work engaged). And, indeed, the regression results indicated that Innovative culture was the one type of organizational culture that contributed significantly to all three facets of employee work engagement.

Supportive culture was another organizational culture that helped explain additional variance, this time in the regression for employees' Emotional work engagement. That result is psychologically reasonable. For example, when managers are supportive by showing they care about employees, trust them, listen to their concerns, and address their needs, employees tend to be happier at their work, and do better work. There is abundant literature on the positive effects of perceived organizational support on employee job satisfaction, affective commitment, and job performance (see Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002).

Bureaucratic culture (the third type of organizational culture), however, did not explain any additional variance in any of the regressions for employee work engagement. This is interesting because of the differences regarding the correlation results. That is, on one hand, Bureaucratic culture had a non-significant correlation with Cognitive work engagement, and a weak correlation with Physical work engagement, so it would not be surprising that Bureaucratic culture did not enter the regression equations for those two facets of work engagement. On the other hand, Bureaucratic culture had a relatively strong

positive correlation with Emotional work engagement, which might lead one to expect this culture to explain some variance in the regression.

However, when two things are kept in mind about these two variables, the reason for Bureaucratic culture not entering the regression may be understood. That is, the positive correlation probably reflects the fact that, in most Asian societies, employees tend to form close personal relationships with their coworkers, which may explain the positive correlation; and, second, also in Asian societies, employees (for ethical reasons) are not inclined to form emotional attachments with their managers or company owners, which could explain the lack of significance in the regression because regressions measure the strength of correlations. In other words, the Asian employees' emotions may be strong with their coworkers, but tend to be relatively weak with their bosses.

7. Conclusions

The limited time frame and financial resources (e.g., to pay interviewers to obtain data) were the main limits of this study. Nonetheless, the data yielded significant results regarding the relationships between employee resilience, organization culture, and work engagement.

Six of the seven hypotheses were fully supported. Four of the first five hypotheses about employee resilience and work engagement received strong support (as follows):

H1: Determination resilience had significant, positive correlations with Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement, which supported H(1a) to H(1c).

H2: Endurance resilience had significant positive correlations with Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement, which supported H(2a) to H(2c).

H3: Adaptability resilience had significant positive correlations with Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement, which supported H(3a) to H(3c).

H4: Recuperability resilience had significant positive correlations with Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement, which supported H(4a) to H(4c).

But hypotheses 5 on organizational culture and work engagement was not supported:

H5: Bureaucratic culture did not have the expected significant negative relationships with Cognitive, Emotional, or Physical work engagement, which did not support H(5a) to H(5c).

However, this contrary outcome revealed new and interesting differences between employees in group-oriented eastern versus individualistic-oriented western cultures regarding Bureaucratic organizational cultures. Specifically, while it was hypothesized that eastern employees would not be work engaged (either cognitively, emotionally, or physically) in Bureaucratic cultures, finding Asian employees positively work engaged was the opposite of what has been found in western culture (Li et al., 2019). Hence, more clarity was added regarding Bureaucratic cultures because the findings revealed the difference in how employees in a group-oriented eastern culture may be expected to respond differently than employees in individualistic-oriented western culture in their work engagement response to Bureaucratic organizational cultures.

The remaining two hypotheses were fully supported:

H6: Innovative organizational culture had significant positive correlations with Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement, which supported H(6a) to H(6c).

H7: Supportive organizational culture had significant positive correlations with Cognitive, Emotional, and Physical work engagement, which supported H(7a) to H(7c).

In summary, the main points of this research were reached. It demonstrated that employee personal resilience does, indeed, relate positively to their work engagement; and that different organizational cultures have differential relationships with work engagement.

7.1. Implications for management

The results of this study may offer insights for managers on how to increase employee work engagement. Whereas the Adaptability facet of personal resilience was the strongest predictor of all three types of work engagement, followed by Determination, managers could improve an employee's Adaptability through certain types of training (Taormina, 2015). For example, Agarwal, Brooks, and Greenberg (2020) found that using a peer support program at work can help colleagues to cope with, and "adapt" to, adverse environments, which is a necessary facet of being resilient. Agarwal et al. also argued that a resilient workforce helps to improve the resilience of the whole organization. Another suggestion made in the literature was to include a program for increasing employees' mental ability to deal with adverse situations and gain the flexibility to adjust themselves psychologically and physically to unfavorable environments under different scenarios (Kuok, Chio, & Pun, 2022).

Another finding was that Innovative organizational culture was a positive predictor of all three facets of work engagement. That is, organizational cultures that reward employees for creating new ideas can increase employee work engagement. For example, during the era when Japan was successfully inventing many new and interesting products, several large corporations scheduled regular meetings every year during which their managers were given long weekends together in a secluded location, and encouraged to "brainstorm" freely to come up with new ideas (which they greatly enjoyed). Therefore, offering employees opportunities to be creative and innovative, and share their ideas without criticism can be effective ways to implement innovative cultures in organizations (Denison, et al., 2013).

8. References

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